

Electrosynthesis and electrochemical studies on polyaniline^ψ

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Electrosynthesis of titanium supported polyaniline films has been carried both under potentiostatic and galvanostatic control. Cyclic voltammetric studies in conjunction with chronoamperometric and potentiometric measurements were employed for the electrochemical characterization of these films. The electrodeposited polyaniline films exhibit acceptable stability and do not undergo any significant determination in their functional activity when subjected to examination of their electrochemical behaviour.

Polyaniline is a conducting polymer of immense contemporary interest^{1,2}. It offers extensive chemical versatility, and functional tunability to meet appropriately the needs of a given application. Its application, in particular, in the development of batteries and sensors are being actively investigated^{3,4}. We describe herein our recent studies on electrochemically grown titanium supported polyaniline films. Both galvanostatic and potentiostatic methods were used for the preparation of these films. For electrochemical characterization, cyclic voltammetric studies in combination with chronoamperometric and chronopotentiometric measurements have been used. These studies indeed show that mechanically sturdy and electrochemically durable polyaniline films endowed with acceptable electrical conductivity can be prepared by using electrodeposition method.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and all solutions were prepared in distilled water. Aniline (B.D.H.) and SDS (C.D.H.) were used as such.

An EG and G Princeton Applied Research 273 potentiostat/galvanostat in combination with a personal computer was used for cyclic voltammetric and chronoamperometric studies. The three-electrode setup used consisted of a platinum working electrode, a titanium counter electrode and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as the reference electrode. The metal electrodes were carefully cleaned and rinsed in acetone and distilled water.

The polyaniline films were anodically synthesized galvanostatically in 1 M HCl aqueous solution containing approximately 5% aniline by volume. The current density

was maintained at 0.1 mA cm⁻² for 15 min to prepare the films. For electrochemical synthesis, a constant current source (LAKE SHORE-120) was used.

Cyclic voltammetric, chronoamperometric and coulometric studies were carried out using platinum and titanium supported polyaniline films using Electrochemical Impedance Measurement System (Model 273) (Princeton Applied Research Corporation, USA).

Results and discussion

Preliminary studies based on examination of the current-voltage behaviour of electroplating solutions containing varied concentrations of aniline in 1 M HCl showed that well bound polyaniline films could be obtained using 5% aniline solutions during electrolysis⁵. The potential domain of electrochemical interest was found to be around 0.70 V to 1.0 V vs SCE. It was also observed that polyaniline films obtained under galvanostatic control using a current density of 1.0 mA/cm² were endowed with acceptable

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms obtained using galvanostatically formed polyaniline in 1 M HCl.

^ψDedicated to Professor Y. K. Gupta on his 80th birth anniversary.

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Fig. 2. Representative cyclic voltammogram of potentiostatically formed polyaniline in 1 M HCl.

mechanical stability for further electrochemical investigations. Representative cyclic voltammograms are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The voltammograms show well resolved peaks corresponding to the two reversible process⁵. Galvanostatically formed polyaniline films invariably showed substantially enhanced conductance in comparison to those obtained potentiostatically under otherwise comparable conditions.

Detailed cyclic voltammetric examination further revealed that the peak potentials for the first redox process varied linearly with the square root of the scan rate. The corresponding peak current however was found to vary linearly with the scan rate conforming to quasi-reversibility of the electron transfer involved⁶.

Fig. 3. Chronoamperometric studies with platinum supported polyaniline film in 1 M HCl at 0.50 V vs SCE.

Galvanostatically grown polyaniline films were also subjected to chronoamperometric examination. A representative chronoamperogram is shown in Fig. 3. Validity of the Cottrell equation⁷

$$I = \frac{n F A D^{1/2} C}{\pi t^{1/2}} \quad (1)$$

where n is number of electron, F , the Faraday constant, D , the diffusion coefficient of the counter-ion in the solution, C , the bulk concentration and A , the area of the electrode; was examined by plotting $I t^{1/2}$ against t . The plots did not yield straight line parallel to the time axis- t consistent with the above equation.

Polyaniline films grown in the presence of the surfactant SDS (sodium dodecyl sulphate) were also subjected to chronoamperometric examination for the estimation of relaxation times at different applied potentials. The capacitance values were then derived using the relationship

$$\tau_t = R \cdot C \quad (2)$$

R denotes resistance and C , the double layer capacitance. These studies show that the polyaniline films obtained in the absence of SDS are endowed with higher capacitance (Table 1). Furthermore, SDS bearing polyaniline films were found to exhibit enhanced conductivity. In view of anionic nature of the immobilized surfactant, facilitated electron transfer to the polyaniline layer is not expected. The electrochemical processes in the presence of surfactant thus seem to exhibit enhanced electron transfer kinetics.

Table 1. Chronopotentiometric study of polyaniline in 1 M HCl

Pt, PAn 1M HCl KCl (sat.) Hg ₂ Cl ₂ Hg, Pt			
Current density (mA cm ⁻²)	Transition time (τ_t , sec)	Relaxation time (τ_r , sec)	Capacitance (μ F)
0.01	38.67	1.960	72.26
0.03	31.33	1.112	85.40
0.50	29.99	0.6906	75.13
0.10	20.00	0.5572	104.30
0.50	16.66	0.4266	311.10
1.00	13.33	0.2742	369.10

Fig. 4. Chronoamperometric behaviour of platinum supported galvanostatically formed polyaniline film.

Chronopotentiometric data were obtained using electrochemically formed polyaniline films at different current densities. A representative plot is given in Fig. 4. Temporal behaviour of the conducting polymer electrode was found to be consistent with the relationship,

$$\phi_t = \phi_0 \cdot e^{-\tau_r/t} \quad (3)$$

The relaxation times estimated from $\log \phi_t$ vs $1/t$ plots; and $1/t$ are given in Table 1 alongwith capacitance values estimated using the relationship 2.

The chronopotentiometric results were also examined in the light of Sand equation⁸.

$$I\tau_t^{1/2} = \frac{nFA\pi^{1/2}D^{1/2}C}{2} \quad (4)$$

τ_t denotes transition time.

$I\tau_t^{1/2}$ when plotted against I does not yield straight line parallel to the current axis (Fig. 5) in accordance with the above equation. Sand's equation strictly holds good under linear diffusion in the absence of kinetic complications. In principle, examination of the variation of $I\tau_t^{1/2}$ vs I , can be used to diagnose processes occurring at the electrode. In

Fig. 5. $I\tau_t^{1/2}$ (mA s^{1/2}) vs I (mA).

Fig. 6. $\Delta I\tau_t^{1/2}$ (mA s^{1/2}) vs I (mA).

our case, positive deviation from Sand's behaviour is observed in all the cases. This behaviour may be attributed accompanying adsorption effects. As the current is increased the transition time does not decrease proportionally. The transition time is longer than under diffusion control because of the adsorbed species. As the current is increased the transition time is always larger since the adsorbed species may make a pronounced contribution. $\Delta I\tau_t^{1/2}$ defined as $(I\tau_t^{1/2})_{\text{obs}} - (I\tau_t^{1/2})_{\text{diff}}$ varies linearly with applied current densities. Since $\Delta I\tau_t^{1/2}$ appears to be a measure of adsorption effect, its progressive increase with applied current density is of interest for the point of view of understanding the involved electrode process.

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References

1. K. Singh and U. Mishra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1997, **36**, 225.
2. K. Singh and U. Mishra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **37**, 613.
3. E. W. Paul, A. J. Rico and M. S. Wrighton, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1985, **80**, 1441.
4. D. A. Kaplin and S. Qtubuddin, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1993, **140**, 3185.
5. K. Singh, U. Mishra and A. K. Tiwari, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1222.
6. A. J. Bard and L. R. Faulkner, "Electrochemical Methods, Fundamentals and Application", John Wiley, New York, 1980.
7. Ilana Fried, "The Chemistry of Electrode Processes", Academic Press, London and New York, 1973.
8. P. T. Kissinger and W. R. Heineman, "Laboratory Techniques in Electroanalytical Chemistry", BAS Press, New York, 1984.